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A Whiteheadian Approach to Self Efficacy and Creative Confidence in Electrical Engineering

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1 INTRODUCTION

A technical university should educate engineers who are competent in their scientific discipline and confident in their own ability to fill important engineering roles [1]. One critical factor in gaining competency and confidence is that students have the opportunity to experience mastery during their education, as these mastery experiences will help them to develop self efficacy [2,3], as well as creative confidence [4].

Self-efficacy is defined by Bandura [1] as a personal judgement of "how well one can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations", and is affected by the following four factors:

1. Experiences of mastery
2. Vicarious experiences ("if they can do it, so can I")
3. Social persuasion
4. Psychological factors.

Of these four factors, *experience of mastery* is identified as the main one, and this is the one we have been focusing on in our study.

In a modern engineering education program, a multitude of subgoals and courses are involved. A successful education program depends on a sound structuring of objectives and learning activities. In the following we describe how A. N. Whitehead's ideas on learning can be applied to a five year integrated master program in Electronic System Design and how an application of these ideas can foster the mastery experiences needed for the development of self efficacy and design confidence. Methods and results are discussed based on three types of student survey.

2 WHITEHEAD'S LEARNING THEORY

A. N. Whitehead's *The Aims of Education* [5] contains 10 essays written in the period 1912–1928. In these essays he criticized the prevailing English education system for teaching *inert ideas*, i.e. "ideas that are merely received into the mind without being utilised, or tested, or thrown into fresh combinations" [5, p.1]. In order to replace the mere transmission of inert ideas with a meaningful education, he outlines a program in the essay *The Rhythm of Education* [5, Ch 2-3]. The idea is that all learning should take place in cycles of three stages:

1. **Romance:** characterized by interest, discovery, curiosity, enthusiasm and exploration.
2. **Precision:** The stage of systematic treatment, formalism, analysis, theory and tools.
3. **Generalization:** The stage of synthesis, application and carrying over of principles to new situations.

Whitehead stresses that, whereas *discipline* is the characteristic of the precision stage, *freedom* should dominate the two others. Thus, a sequence of learning cycles will give an alteration between freedom and discipline. Within each of the three stages, there will be sequences of cycles within cycles: "the development of mentality exhibits itself as a rhythm involving an interweaving of cycles, the whole process being dominated by a greater cycle of the same general character as its minor eddies" [5, p. 27]. It is this rhythm that provides a

balance between discipline and freedom in students' learning experiences.

The three stages each provide three essential stimuli: *the evocation of interest*, *the acquirement of technique*, and *the excitement of success* [5, p. 38]. Students often experience the stages when discipline is required as the "hard" part of education. In order for the students to be motivated for these parts, they should not lose the inspiration from the romance stage. An anticipation of success in the generalization stage is also a source of motivation for bringing them through the sometime "dull" precision stages.

An emergent question then is whether Whitehead's ideas remain relevant for modern engineering education and how they might be applied. According to Whitehead's scheme, an education program should start with student activities having elements of curiosity, exploration and discovery giving experiences motivating for the next step, which is precision. This is very much in line with contemporary ideas about integrating project- and problem-based learning into first year engineering curricula [6]. Following Whitehead, precision, with its emphasis on discipline, analysis and tools, should not be introduced before the students have some knowledge of and experience with the concepts and phenomena the theory focus on and tools handle. Finally, students can gain from the tools learned in the precision part in order to perform on a higher level during the generalization stage.

Traditionally, engineering programs finalize the education with a capstone project where the candidates show that they have attained the competence for independently fulfilling a task within their discipline. Before that project, a large body of courses secure that necessary technical and methodical knowledge is acquired. Such courses fall well into Whitehead's precision category, whereas the capstone project is an example of generalization. What is often missing is a sufficient amount of romance. For some subjects in the engineering curriculum, such as mathematics, the romance stage should already be passed during high school, and the students are ripe for further precision. In technological topics, this is not necessarily the case for most students. Therefore, we argue that an engineering program should set aside at least one year where romance is the keynote.

3 AN EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION

The program Electronic System Design and Innovation (Elsys) at The Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) was established in 2014 with curriculum built around Whitehead's threefold rhythm. The overall structure of the program is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Example of ten semester program with Whiteheadian "cycles within cycles".

The program is a five year integrated master program (no bachelor degree after three years), where the first four semesters have a romance key note, followed by four semesters of precision before the final year which is devoted mainly to a master project constituting the main generalization stage. Within the romance stage, a sequence of four courses *The Electronic Engineering Ladder* [7–8] comprises in itself a Romance-Precision-Generalization (RPG) cycle. The first semester is dominated by a course (Introduction to Electronic System design) where the students do a project working in teams. Intermingled with the project work, there are guest lectures from industry presenting role models discussing future career possibilities and the need for electronic system design. This course mainly falls into the romance category. This stage of romance is thus intended to give motivating momentum for the two next semesters, which are devoted to precision. During semester two and three of the Engineering Ladder, the course *Electronic System Design and Analysis (ESDA)* is given, before the project from the first semester is taken up in the fourth semester providing generalization of the competence gained from the two preceding precision flavoured semesters.

Note that the terms *romance*, *precision* and *generalization* indicate key notes, i.e. the prevailing atmosphere that colours the student's experience. Taking a closer look at the ESDA course with a key note in precision, it is organized as eight smaller RPG-cycles. Thus a "fractal" structure is obtained with cycles within cycles, as prescribed by Whitehead.

During the two ESDA semesters the students should apprehend several abstract theoretical concepts such as impedance, frequency response and signal spectra. In addition, they should become familiar with components such as transistors and operational amplifiers. This requires applications of mathematics, advanced instruments and models of electronic components. Students should also train to develop their creative skills in designing simple electronic systems.

As illustrated in figure 1, the structure of this course, where the key note is precision, is made up as a sequence of several three-week cycles. Within each cycle, the first week is focused on a video lecture, giving motivation and also presenting some theoretical concepts, after which students and instructor meet in class for discussions at a conceptual level.

The discussion is based on principles from *peer instruction* [9] where multiple choice problems are given in the classroom and student responses are recorded by a student response tool using smartphones and laptops. The problems are of a conceptual type not requiring calculations but an actual understanding of the underlying principles. Since the formal methodology required for exact calculations is left out at this stage, the week can be said to play a romance role in the cycle.

After the conceptual discussions, exercises are handed out that require mathematical, analytical and experimental skills. This type of precision work takes up the next week. Finally, a week is set aside for generalization through an individual design project, thus completing an RPG sub cycle.

In contrast to traditional exercises and exams, the experience of having completed eight design projects, which are more similar to what an engineer would do, this kind of mastery experiences should give students the opportunity to better develop their self-efficacy through the experience of mastery.

One challenge here is to align the activities in the ESDA course with the assessment practices, as learning relevant for a future career, becomes manifest primarily during the generalization stage, which is not so easy to test on an exam.

In the ESDA course, the generalization stages are organized as eight individual design projects, D1-D8, and the intention is that as many students as possible shall enjoy success and an experience of mastery during these eight projects. A short report, typically 5-10 pages, is required from each student, and these reports count towards the final grade together with a written exam. Only one week is allotted to each design project, but the students are allowed to hand in improved versions of each report until the end of the semester. It is stressed that the grading of the report depends not on the quality of the design but on how it is documented. Thus, a faulty design can result in a top grade if the report presents an adequate discussion of the failure. By this emphasis, we attempt to reduce performance anxiety during the design process that could otherwise hamper creativity and initiative.

Students are encouraged to help each other during each design projects. Instructors and assistants are also present to provide guidance. To ensure individual learning, each student is given individual specifications. To encourage creativity, the students are free to choose their own approach to solving the problem, but we furnish information to how one *might* proceed.

4 EXPLORING STUDENT EXPERIENCES

Three types of survey have been used in order to assess the impact of the program structure. One is "Studiebarometeret"; a national survey conducted each year among students of all Norwegian University and College programs. In addition, we have used a questionnaire issued at the end of each course. Finally, a poll is performed after the completion of each of the eight design projects during the ESDA course.

4.1 Overall student satisfaction

A national survey is performed annually probing student satisfaction in all Norwegian programs of higher education. At NTNU a traditional program of electrical engineering was phased out as the new Elsys program was introduced. A comparison of the two programs with respect to student satisfaction is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overall student satisfaction for the traditional electronic engineering program (red) and the new approach (blue). Number n of survey participants is shown for each data point.

Average score for all Norwegian programs is 4.0, meaning that both programs have fairly good results. Very few programs, reach 4.6 or 4.7, indicating that the new approach gives a substantial improvement in student satisfaction. Since the new program emphasizes application of skills, it is reasonable to interpret the rise as a rise in mastery experience as well.

4.2 Experience of mastery

In an attempt to measure the degree of mastery experience, a survey was given to the students after the completion of each design project, where the students are asked to express their subjective experience of mastery with the alternatives *little degree*, *some degree* or *large degree*. They were also asked to assess the workload and difficulty of the assignment compared to earlier ones². The distribution of the answers, collected autumn 2017 and spring 2018 in percentage are summarized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of answers on survey about student experience during design projects 1-8 in the ESDA course. Data for D5 and D6 are not available. Number of participants n in survey is indicated at the bottom.

From the figure, it is evident that the degree of mastery experience varies among the students. For the majority of the projects, "some degree of mastery" is the most common answer, except for D4 and D8, with "small degree" and "large degree" respectively.

There is also quite some variability with respect to workload and difficulty. Not surprisingly, these parameters are quite correlated.

4.3 In students' own words

At the end of semester two and three, the students were asked to reflect upon the course in general and respond a number of open-ended questions. One thing that emerges from these

² For project D1, where no earlier projects were available, the respondents were asked to compare workload and difficulty with a regular weekly assignment.

reflections is the importance of the design projects. The students describe the projects help them to connect theory to practice and to experience mastery:

“I enjoyed the design projects especially well, then you get to combine theory with practice. You were also “forced” to work individually with these projects and develop an understanding early in the semester. This gave me an experience of mastery”

The students, further, explain that achieving a solution after working on a difficult project makes them feel satisfied:

“It is a really good feeling to finally get a working solution on a design project.”

It is this feeling of satisfaction and mastery that motivates the students to work on the new problems and helps them to go through the precision stage of the next RPG cycle. If, however, the experience of difficulty is too high, the design projects can have unintended consequences and lead to frustration instead of experience of mastery:

“When the design projects work, they are really good tools for creating an understanding, but when you do not really get it working, frustration and low willingness to learn can quickly arise.”

One important factor that the students highlight for a well-designed design project is a suitable workload, with some students reporting a fair amount of work required to complete the projects, while others relate that the workload can be too high:

“Even though the design projects are very educational, the workload can be a bit high.”

Another challenge that the students describe in their reflections is their uncertainty about the scope of the design projects. The students explain that it can be difficult to directly understand what is expected within the design project and that this can limit opportunities to experience mastery:

“With many of the design projects, it was difficult to know what was expected to be able to achieve, this resulted in a lot of insecurity.”

It is through careful scaffolding, continuous formative assessment, and feedback that this uncertainty can be reduced and the students can feel that they have control of the situation. In summary, the students report that the design projects give a feeling of mastery, however, also emphasizing that the projects need to be well designed with respect to both difficulty and workload.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the initial empirical data of students' experiences of the ESDA and particularly their experience of mastery, the design projects have a large potential, but need to be framed and scaffolded carefully. It is a recurring challenge in PBL to formulate problems that both result in intended learning objectives and are adapted to the level of the students. The challenge is escalated when the body of students encompasses a large variety of skills and understanding. In addition, the current university admission system, where students are admitted based on their grades from upper secondary school, creates additional problems. For the Elsys program the requirements are rather high. This means that most students will have strategies that are adapted to solve standard textbook problems and perform very well on that type of

tasks. The independent design problems D1-D8, present, however, a new kind of challenge for most students, and the ability to meet this challenge varies to a high degree across the student population.

For an engineer, self-efficacy should encompass mastery of method and tools, as well as the less specific quality of *creative confidence*. Although both qualities should be developed during the education, their emphasis will vary. With only a week available for each design project, the attained degree of mastery/self efficacy will most likely be experienced with respect to methods and tools. This corresponds well with the projects taking place within a *precision* sub cycle. As mentioned, some hints as how to go about with the design are given initially, and most students follow these hints. There are, however, some students who eagerly try to find their own way also in these short projects. For the majority, creative confidence is mostly developed during the generalization stage in the fourth semester of the Electronic Engineering Ladder [8].

We have, based on a framework inspired by Whitehead, implemented a three stage rhythm including *romance*, *precision* and *generalization* in an electrical engineering program, with special focus on the first two years. By using his rather simple principles as guiding posts, we have given an example of how to organize a study program resulting in increased student satisfaction, and engineers with well-founded self-efficacy. Generally, by letting imagination and freedom be in focus during the romance and generalization stages, we avoid that the precise knowledge gained in the precision phases becomes inert and passive, with the result of increased understanding.

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